

1 **Epigenetic control of immunity by SUV420H2.**

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6 We describe here control of the immune system in higher organisms by SUV420H2. Epigenetic control of
7 immune system components appeared to be a programmatically designed aspect of SUV420H2 function
8 rather than a consequence of general differences in epigenetic targeting. SUV420H2 exerted specific
9 control of Ig-like receptors including *IGDCC4* and *IGSF9*. The IL-1 receptor system, including IL-1a and
10 IL-1B, the complement pathway, and genes with thrombotic function including *TFPI* were also targets of
11 SUV420H2 control indicating SUV420H2 also possesses specialized innate immunity regulatory
12 properties.
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